

Introducing the DORIS README template

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Introducing the DORIS README template

A README is a guide to your dataset. Use the accompanying *README.txt* template to assist other researchers to understand your dataset, how its contents are structured, and how to use the data.

The DORIS *README.txt* template file.

The accompanying file *README.txt* is a template that you can use when submitting datasets for Researchdata.se using SND's DORIS. The headings and lists in *README.txt* will help you to include relevant information. Each heading or list-item is followed by a short explanation of what information should be provided – delete the explanations and replace them with the information that is relevant for your own dataset. If a particular item is not relevant, either delete the entire item or just replace the explanatory text with “N/A”.

The *README.txt* template will hopefully provide you with enough structure and sufficient hints that you can use it to make a great README for your dataset without reading this document! This document explains the purpose of a README file in more detail, gives more examples of what a README can contain, and has extra tips for writing README files, even for other repositories.

See [SND's information page for DORIS](#) for more information about submitting datasets using DORIS.

The README in context

A dataset's *documentation* and *metadata* (see below) should together provide sufficient detail so that other researchers can:

- understand what the data represents, and how the dataset's contents should be interpreted,
- understand how the data are structured, and how they can be read using appropriate software, and
- evaluate whether the data are suitable for a new purpose.

The dataset *metadata* is the information that you enter in DORIS when you submit your dataset (Title, Description, Author etc.). The metadata are shown in the Researchdata.se catalog when your dataset is published. Good metadata allows others to find your dataset using suitable search terms.

The dataset *documentation* comprises other documents that describe the contents of the dataset in more detail. Documentation files can be uploaded in DORIS or supplied as links or citations. Good documentation allows people who have found your dataset to understand how the dataset was created, what it contains, whether it is suitable for their purposes, and how to use the data.

Documentation usually includes a report, a reference to a scientific article, or some similar document that describes the dataset's origin. Simply referring to such an article or report, however, rarely enables a secondary user to interpret the contents of the dataset's datafiles with certainty. A research article may explain, for example, how a particular data variable was collected and analyzed. But research articles do not usually describe which datafile contains the variable, what the variable is named in the datafile, which units are used, or how quality codes are used for missing values.

The purpose of the README file is to describe the dataset's contents and structure. If there is an associated research article or report, README should allow other researchers to understand how the contents of the data files relate to the research described in the article or report.

If there is no existing scientific article or report that details how the data were collected or created, we recommend creating a documentation file with this information and uploading it independently of the README. This keeps the README focused on the content of the dataset itself. Further, describing data collection or research methodologies often requires figures, images or equations, whereas a README should use a simple file format.

What should the README contain?

This section has an overview of the elements in the README.txt template.

1. Basic Metadata

The README should include some essential information that allows the dataset to be identified and informs users of their legal rights to use the data.

When submitting datasets vis SND's DORIS, there is no need to include all the information that is already reported as metadata (Affiliations, Acknowledgement of funding sources, etc.) also in the README!

Avoid including a lot of administrative metadata and aim to provide a 'technical overview' of the dataset.

- **Dataset title, recommended citation ("reference") and responsible organization:**
The title of the dataset should be included, along with the dataset's citation and DOI. In addition to facilitating basic attribution, this makes it possible to find the dataset's catalog entry in Researchdata.se.

For privacy reasons, avoid email addresses in the README - public contact information can be provided in DORIS, or via your ORCID profile.
- A short description of the dataset to help users understand the dataset's **content**, context and relevance. Copy or summarize the description from the metadata.
- State any **license** or **terms of use** you are imposing. Any dataset license should match the license specification given in DORIS. However, the files in a dataset may have different terms of use (e.g. datafiles you created with a CC BY license, datafiles redistributed from another dataset with a CC BY-SA license, and photographs that are copyright), and you should explain such distinctions in your README.

If your dataset includes data sourced from other datasets then you should also include information on the data sources, perhaps later in the README (see Reference Information, below).

- Describe any **access restrictions**. If the dataset cannot be legally redistributed by third parties (for example, because it contains sensitive data) indicate how copies can be legally obtained. The README template has an example formulation.

2. Essential information for dataset reuse.

Provide essential information that secondary users *will need to know* in order to reuse the dataset or understand its contents. You can include a simplified description of the methodology that was used to create the dataset if you wish, but do not aim for a comprehensive description of the entire process here.

Essential information commonly included in README files includes:

- information about sampling, experiment or survey configurations, which is especially important if different datafiles contain measurements for different times, locations, levels, population samples, etc.
- the locations or coordinates of sampling sites (may be listed in a separate file if there are many sites).
- the geographical coordinate reference system used in GIS datafiles (if not specified in the datafiles themselves).
- information about unusual file formats – what software or software libraries can be used to read these files?
- the search and filter terms used in database searches that yielded the dataset.
- important policies or algorithms for masking or outlier removal.

If the dataset includes code, provide instructions for how to run the code. Similarly, if software was used to generate the data and the software is available from a source code repository, provide a link to the repository. Provide information about the versions of the software environment and libraries that you used when running the code, along with any configurable parameters or other inputs.

3. Dataset organization.

Your aim here is to provide an overview of the data and documentation files. For simpler datasets with few files and no zip-files or subfolders, you can skip this section and simply describe the datafiles.

The contents of datafiles are often interrelated, typically through sample- or respondent-IDs. If so, explain how the data files are connected to each other, and which documentation files correspond to which data files, where appropriate.

If many files/folders have the same format but contain data for different experiments/samples/etc., describe the file/folder naming convention and how it identifies the associated experiment/sample/etc.

If the dataset has nested folders, it can be useful to embed short explanations in a visual map of the dataset:

```
README.txt
Folder_A/
  Files for experiment A
Folder_B/
  Sub_Folder_1/
    Data files for experiment B for thing 1
  Sub_Folder_2/
    Data files for experiment B for thing 2
```

4. Datafile descriptions.

For each type of file or folder in the dataset, provide a short, generalized description of what it contains.

For hierarchical datafiles (e.g. .xlsx files with sheets, or nested data structures in .mat or .json format), describe how the contents are organized. Describe any formatting (especially colors) used in .xlsx files.

For tabular datafiles (e.g. .csv or .xlsx files) with relatively few variables, you can include an inventory of each file's contents in the README. For each file:

- Summarize what is contained in the file. One sentence is usually sufficient.
- Describe each of the variables in a few words.
- Give the units for the variables, state any conventions used, or explain the meanings of codes and classifications.

Example:

```
Weather.csv - composite hourly weather timeseries.
```

Columns:

```
Date [yyyy-mm-dd]. Date.
```

```
Hour [hh]. Hour, local timezone (CET+1), no daylight savings. Data for hour 00 cover the interval 00:00≤hour<01:00.
```

```
Temp [°C]. Average temperature.
```

```
Temp_code [numeric, 1-3]. Source code flag for Temp: 1=average of observed values, 2=average of nearby stations, 3=average of preceding and following hours.
```

For more complex data files (e.g. survey results), the file's contents are usually described with separate documentation files (codebooks, question lists, etc.) and the README should rather explain how the various files are related.

5. Reference information

Finally, provide non-essential and reference information. Include here information that other researchers in your own field will already know but which researchers from other fields may need. The following list covers some information that can be included for reference.

- **Abbreviations** used in file or folder names, along with how these relate to information in other documents.

- For aggregated datasets (those that include data from other datasets), list the **data sources**, summarize why you have permission to reuse these data (e.g. a license, you obtained private permission, the data are in the public domain), and indicate which data in your dataset come from which sources. If your dataset includes secondary data from a larger number of sources (>10), the information can be included in a separate file, and you can simply refer to it here.
- If the dataset contains static copies of files that are under **version control** (usually source code files on a Git repository), note this and provide a link to the main repository.
- Note any issues with **data quality** that you think a secondary user would benefit from knowing. This could be quality assurance work (data validation, checking) you have performed, data manipulations or modifications, known biases, missing data, or other limitations. You do not need to include lots of details in the README, especially if the details are already described in other documentation files! However, it is important to let a dataset user know if and how you have validated the data, and where they can find more information.
- Any **considerations regarding reuse**, such as potential limitations or best practices, can be mentioned.

Can I use another file format for the README?

Our README template is a plain-text file. You can also use markdown (.md), hypertext (.html) or Word (.docx) format for your README.

If you provide a README as a PDF, you should also provide an editable source document (e.g. .tex, .md, .html, .docx) from which the PDF was generated. This makes it easier to revise the README if the dataset is updated with a new version later.

We recommend that text and markdown files are UTF-8 encoded.

Tips for writing a README

In this section we have collated some general advice that might help you write better READMEs.

Firstly, a few points that are often mentioned as best-practice for writing data documentation generally are:

- Always try to describe the data files as clearly as possible.
- Do not use jargon
- Define terms and acronyms
- State data limitations, if these are important. But be specific and quantify statements about data quality.

Secondly, a good README is tailored for the kind of material you publish and the research field to which it belongs. For example, a README for a genomics dataset might describe what the different sequence files contain (nuclear genome, mitochondrial sequences, fragments etc.)

and how the sequences are annotated. A README for an economics dataset, on the other hand, might concentrate on data sources, collection periods, and descriptions of key variables.

Finally, the single most effective way to create a great README is to document your work as you go! If you wait until the end of your project, you might already have lost or forgotten valuable information. Get into the habit of documenting data files with README-style information when you create them. This helps ensure that important details do not get lost, and means it takes less work to create your README when you come to publishing the data!

Further considerations

If you share research data without rich metadata, or if your dataset is so complex that the advice in this document is difficult to implement, this section is for you.

Datasets without “rich metadata” or other documentation.

If you are going to share a dataset via a file-sharing service (ftp-server or cloud server), or if you submit to a repository that does not support “rich metadata”, then you should include more metadata in the README. For example, if the web-form for the metadata only allows you to describe the dataset’s creators with their names, then the README should include sufficient information to uniquely identify the creators: their names, organizations, departments, and preferably their ORCIDs.

How can I organize more complex information?

You can include more than one README in a dataset! If the dataset has subfolders, you can include a README for a particular folder.

If your datafiles contain a lot of variables, it can be more practical to include the descriptions of the datafiles’ variables as separate files. One additional advantage of this approach is that the variables can be described in a file with a more structured format (.csv, .xlsx, .json) that is more machine-readable.

Acknowledgements

While preparing this guide, we took inspiration from [PUBLIC UBC RDM Documents](#), the [README file example developed by Cornell University](#), and [Best Practices for Data Submission in Generalist Repositories: A Checklist](#).

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